

Constitution of the Colouring Matter of *Lawsonia Alba* Lam., or Indian Mehedi.

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Lawsonia alba (N. O. Lythraceae) or Meneai as it is known in Bengali and Hindi and Henna in English is an ornamental garden shrub or hedge plant of purely Indian origin, but which has for some time been cultivated in Persia, Arabia, Mesopotamia, Egypt, Northern Africa and Southern Europe for the sake of the colouring matter contained in the leaves, which is very much prized in these countries as a dye for the hair, fingers and nails. From the point of view of Indian medicine, practically every part of the plant has found some application or other, and is used all over the country in disorders of the liver and spleen, urinary calculi, leprosy and other obstinate types of skin diseases.

But probably the most important constituent of the plant is the colouring matter contained in the leaves, which can be easily extracted by maceration with water or dilute alkali. In the state of these solutions the colouring matter has a most powerful affinity for the skin and hair and dyes an exceedingly fast shade.

There is absolutely no record of any work done on the constitution of the active principle of Indian lawsonia, although as early as 1868, Herraory (*Journal de Pharmacy*, 1863, Jan.) working on the European variety, isolated from it a tannin, which he named henno-tannic acid. It was a brown resin answering in all its chemical properties to ordinary tannin. Later on Thomson (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1878, 21, 2, 483) showed that the colouring matter obtained in this way was soluble in glycerin, in ammonia, in solutions of soda and potash and in dilute acids. More recently Tommasi (*Gazzetta*, 1920, 80, 263) working on the European variety of *Lawsonia* isolated from it a crystalline colouring matter melting at 192-95° (decomp.), which he named *Lawsonone* on account of its ketonic nature and which he found to possess the formula $C_{10}H_8O_3$. He also prepared the calcium salt, the acetyl derivative and the reduced acetyl derivative of the colouring matter.

The above represents the work that has been done on the European variety of *Lawsonia*, the Indian variety of the plant having remained practically untouched up to this time. On account of the great importance of the plant from the Indian medical point of view,

it was thought advisable by the present authors to take it under examination.

The colouring matter was prepared from the fresh leaves in a perfectly pure condition by an elaborate process including several crystallisations from benzene and acetone. It was thereby obtained in cauliflower like clusters of needles with a dark mahogany colour and metallic reflex, which when crushed in a mortar became reduced to a lemon yellow powder. It melted sharp at 190° (decomp.) and the melting point did not rise even on repeated crystallisations from various solvents. Analytical data and a number of molecular weight determinations established the molecular formula as $C_{10}H_6O_3$, and the preparation of monoacetyl and monobenzoyl derivatives, mono- and dioximes, phenylhydrazone, etc., showed that the substance contains phenolic hydroxy and two ketonic groups. These, together with the fact that on distillation with zinc dust it became practically quantitatively converted into naphthalene and that it possesses a persistent quinone like odour reminding of α -naphthoquinone, the conclusion was almost irresistible that it must be a hydroxy- α -naphthoquinone. The position of the hydroxy group must be in the same nucleus which contains the quinone grouping, since on oxidation with potassium permanganate it gave rise to only phthalic acid and nothing else. Hence the only possible constitution of the colouring matter, which has also been named *lawsone* by the present authors, is that it must be 2-hydroxy- α -naphthoquinone. And this has been confirmed by a direct comparison of lawsone and its derivatives with synthetically prepared 2-hydroxy- α -naphthoquinone and the corresponding derivatives prepared from the same substance as the following table will show:

Prepared from the plant.	M.p.	Synthetically prepared.	M.p.	Mixed m.p.
Lawsone	190°	2-Hydroxy- α -N*	190°	190°
Acetyl-lawsone	128-29°	2-Acetoxy- α -N	128-30°	129°
Anilinolawsone	190°	2-Anilino- α -N	190°	190°
Triacetyldihydro-lawsone	134.5°	1:2:4-Triacetoxy-naphthalene	134.5°	134°
Lawsone phenylhydrazone	229°	Benzeneazo-naphthresorcin	229°	229°
Lawsone mono-oxime	180°	2-Hydroxy- α -N-oxime	180°	180°
Monobromolawsone	198°	2-Hydroxy-3-bromo- α -N.	198.5°	198°
Lawsone ethylether	126-27°	2-Hydroxy- α -N-ethylether	126°	126°

* N = naphthoquinone.

By a glance at the above table and comparing it with the work done by Tommasi (*loc. cit.*) it becomes quite evident that the compound he obtained from European *Lawsonia* was in all probability identical with the lawsone obtained by the present authors from Indian *Lawsonia* in spite of small difference in the melting point as reported by him. In other words the Indian and the European varieties of *Lawsonia* probably contain the same colouring matter lawsone, which is identical with 2-hydroxy- α -naphthoquinone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of lawsone.—Five kilos of the *fresh* leaves were crushed in a stone mortar (iron should not be used) and extracted with a 5% solution of sodium bicarbonate, three times in succession, for a period of 24 hours each, in large enamelled iron basin. After the third extraction the leaves were practically devoid of colour and the combined extracts were acidified with strong sulphuric acid diluted with an equal volume of water. The resultant voluminous precipitate which consisted of the crude colouring matter was filtered off and dried and a further small quantity was obtained by saturating the filtrate with common salt and filtering again. The crude substance was then extracted with dilute ammonium hydroxide, filtered and the filtrate precipitated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the process repeated twice. Finally the precipitate after drying, was extracted with benzene and the solvent distilled off when the colouring matter was obtained in the form of orange-yellow crusts, melting at 185-88°. It was then dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, filtered and the orange-yellow filtrate precipitated with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered, washed with distilled water until free from chloride, dried and repeatedly crystallised from benzene and acetone until the melting point went up to 190° and did not rise any further. The substance thus isolated has a dark mahogany-bronze colour in the crystalline and a lemon-yellow colour in the powdered state, yield 2.5 g. or .05% of the weight of the fresh leaves.

The substance is very sparingly soluble in cold water with an orange-yellow colour and the solution undergoes decomposition on boiling. It is slightly soluble in chloroform, bromoform, acetic acid, benzene and petroleum ether and moderately soluble in alcohol, benzene and ether. The solution in all these solvents has a bright orange-yellow colour. It is very easily soluble in solutions of alkali

carbonates, bicarbonates and hydroxides, forming orange-red solutions which quickly undergo decomposition when boiled. In the cold the colouring matter can be reprecipitated unchanged from the above solutions by treatment with dilute acids. The substance is fairly acidic in reaction and produces a brisk evolution of carbon dioxide from sodium bicarbonate although not from sodium carbonate. It is also feebly acidic to litmus paper in aqueous or aqueous alcoholic solution. Alcoholic solution of the substance gives an immediate orange precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate, but does not give any precipitate with either alcoholic silver nitrate, copper acetate, nickel acetate, ferric chloride or calcium chloride, although a deep red colour is developed with nickel acetate and a reddish brown colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 69.18, 69.12, 69.01; H, 3.51, 3.52, 3.47; M. W. 170, 177, 178. (b. p. method in acetone); 172, 175 (silver salt); 176.5, 175.5 (lead salt). $C_{10}H_6O_3$ requires C, 68.9; H, 3.4 per cent. and M. W. 174).

Silver salt.—To an alcoholic solution of lawsone (1 g.) neutralised by the addition of a few drops of dilute ammonia, alcoholic silver nitrate was added until the red precipitate was no longer formed. This was filtered off, washed and dried. Red amorphous substance resembling cinnabar in appearance. (Found: C, 42.82; H, 1.81; Ag, 38.67, 38.39. $C_{10}H_5O_3Ag$ requires C, 42.71; H, 1.78; Ag, 38.44 per cent).

Ammonium salt was obtained by dissolving lawsone (1 g.) in the smallest quantity of concentrated ammonia and allowing the solution to evaporate completely at the ordinary temperature. Bright red crystalline substance, exceedingly soluble in water and alcohol and decomposing between 150-70° without melting. (Found: C, 63.55; H, 5.59. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.83; H, 5.93 per cent).

Neutral lead salt.—To an aqueous solution of the ammonium salt prepared as above, aqueous lead acetate was added when an amorphous yellow precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, washed and dried. (Found: C, 43.09; H, 2.02; Pb, 37.14. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6Pb$ requires C, 43.32; H, 1.80; Pb, 37.55 per cent).

Lead acetate double salt.—To an alcoholic solution of lawsone, alcoholic lead acetate was added drop by drop, until the precipitate was no longer formed. This was filtered off, washed with alcohol and dried. Bright orange glistening plates, slightly soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: C, 32.77; H, 2.04; Pb, 47.5. $C_{10}H_5O_3 \cdot Pb \cdot COCH_3$ requires C, 32.73; H, 1.82; Pb, 47.28 per cent).

Sodium salt was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide to a solution of lawsone in dilute sodium hydroxide. The glistening red crystalline precipitate was filtered through asbestos and dried in the vacuum desiccator. It could not however be obtained in a sufficiently pure state for analysis.

Acetyl-lawsone was prepared from lawsone and acetic anhydride in the usual manner. It crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow plates, m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 66.43; H, 3.98. $C_{10}H_5O_3 \cdot COCH_3$ requires C, 66.66; H, 3.79 per cent).

Triacetyldihydrolawsone.—Lawsone (2 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (10 g.) under reflux and moist zinc dust gradually added until the solution was completely decolourised. The mixture was then filtered into cold water and stirred and the resulting white precipitate filtered off and crystallised from dilute alcohol in lustrous white laminæ, m.p. 134.5°. (Found: C, 63.38; H, 4.72. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 63.45; H, 4.68 per cent).

Anilinolawsone.—A mixture of lawsone (2 g.), aniline (4 g.) and glacial acetic acid (8 g.) was heated under reflux for 3 hours and then poured into water. The resulting dark red precipitate was filtered off and crystallised from alcohol in long scarlet needles, m.p. 190°. (Found: C, 76.89; H, 4.55. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 77.10; H, 4.41 per cent).

Lawsone mono-oxime was prepared from lawsone (1 mol.) and hydroxylamine acetate (1 mol.) in the usual manner. It crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow needles, m.p. 180°. It dissolves in alkalis and organic solvents with a bright yellow colour. It is a powerful dyestuff. (Found: C, 63.35; H, 3.87. $C_{10}H_6O_2 \cdot NOH$ requires C, 63.49; H, 3.70 per cent).

Lawsone dioxime was obtained by treating lawsone with a slightly more than the theoretical quantity of hydroxylamine. The substance crystallised from alcohol in light yellow glistening needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.75. $C_{10}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.46 per cent).

Lawsone phenylhydrazone.—A mixture of lawsone (0.8 g.), phenylhydrazine (0.5 g.) and alcohol (2 c.c.) was allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for 12 hours and then cautiously diluted with water. The phenylhydrazone separated in scarlet-red prisms which were crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 229° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.57. $C_{16}H_8O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.76 per cent).

Lawsone ethyl ether.—A mixture of the silver salt of lawsone (4 g.) and ethyl bromide (2 g.) was heated in a pressure flask on the

water-bath for 4 hours. After cooling the bottle was opened, the excess of ethyl bromide evaporated off and the residue extracted with alcohol and the filtered extract allowed to stand when the ethyl ether crystallised out in glistening yellow needles, m.p. 126-27°.

Monobromolawsone.—Lawsone (1 g.) dissolved in warm acetic acid was treated with an acetic acid solution of bromine, until it was no longer decolourised even on boiling. On cooling, the bromo derivative crystallised out in yellow prisms which were recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198°. (Found : Br, 32.2. $C_{10}H_5O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.6 per cent).

Distillation of lawsone with zinc dust.—Lawsone, on distillation with zinc dust in a current of hydrogen in the usual manner, gave an almost quantitative yield of naphthalene.

Oxidation of lawsone with alkaline potassium permanganate.—Lawsone (5 g.) dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide was treated with a 3% aqueous solution of potassium permanganate until the latter was no longer decolourised. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off, the filtrate evaporated to a small volume and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when masses of colourless needles (m.p. 213°) gradually separated which were identified to be phthalic acid. No other product could be detected.

Benzeneazolawsone.—Aniline was diazotised and coupled with lawsone dissolved in excess of dilute sodium hydroxide. A red precipitate, insoluble in water or alkalis was produced, which was filtered off, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and water and finally crystallised from alcohol in scarlet needles melting above 305°. The substance could not be obtained in sufficient quantity for complete examination.